

Introduction

This paper investigates the River Severn and Carno as they pass through Caersws, Wales, see figure 1. Specifically, qualities such as water temperature, sediment particle size, heavy metal concentrations and flow velocity and their spatial, temporal and climactic relationships. Caersws was home to an important railway link in the 1870s which transported lead from the Van Mines in Llanidloes, located only 11km upstream of Caersws (Grosvenor, 2021). Current land-use in Caersws is mostly attributed to grasslands and pastures for cattle raising and other livestock, with little to no growth of arable crops (CPAT, 2024). The past and present land-use is important to understand how it might impact and interact with the measured river qualities. It is especially important to Natural England, who wish to make the area around Caersws and the River Severn a ‘Site of Specific Scientific Interest’ (SSSI), and to do so they must first understand the area and the threats it faces from human activities. By understanding the current environmental conditions, it will be possible to accurately evaluate the impact of any conservation practices later imposed on the site. It is further important to be able to analyze the methodology used to describe the data, whose secondary aspect makes an evaluation more necessary. The report will be organized surrounding the respective research questions, with contextual information, methods, analysis, and result interpretation, lastly, critical evaluation of these methods. These research questions are as follows:

1. What is the water temperature of the River Severn over the assessment period, and does it vary across the year?
2. How does the particle size of river sediments vary in different parts of the River Severn?
3. Are there any differences in heavy metal concentrations on the River Severn upstream and downstream of the River Carno?
4. How does river flow velocity of the River Severn at Caersws relate to climate?

Figure 1: DigiMap of site-specific data on the River Severn and Caersws, Wales. The ‘Site of Specific Scientific Interest’ (dark blue line) holds within it the points SEV-1 (red) used to measure water temperature daily, SEV-A, -B, -C and -D (green) which denote the locations of particle size observations in the river sediments, SEV- upstream, -downstream, and CARNO (purple) demonstrate the sampling locations of the heavy metal concentrations, and the triangle (black and white) which shows the distance and easterly direction of the Newton meteorological and gauging station- where the climactic data such as wind speed and air temperature were collected.

Main Body

1. The first research question concerns water temperature in the River Severn at point SEV-1 over the assessment period and how it varies over the year. Many biological and chemical processes are controlled by water temperature; therefore, it is important to understand the flow systems in place in the river. In lowland temperate systems such as that of Caersws and the River Severn, water and air temperature tend to directly relate to each other. The data, from 2017, is observed by the Environment Agency and though the precise time and date are not represented in the data, each observation is attributed to a month which allows for analysis of seasonality. The data analysis methods used for this research question are basic descriptive statistics including

sample size, minimum, maximum, range, median, 1st and 3rd quartiles and the interquartile range, along with average and standard deviation. These methods were chosen to simplify the data and coherently demonstrate main ideas.

Figure 2: Box and Whisker Plot of Monthly Water Temperature in point SEV-1 River Severn, Caersws, Wales 2017. Colors correspond in chronological order to those on the graph (left to right), error bars = exclusive median quartile calculation, outliers = dots (June and December data), n = number listed before respective month (legend), temperature = continuous interval, time = discrete ratio data

A common trend in the northern hemisphere of warmer summer months is reflected in the water temperature data, figure 2, with warmest months being June, July and August. Interestingly, August has the highest mean temperature, but June and July experienced higher temperatures or more temperature variability than August. Unsurprisingly, January, February and December are the cooler months with very small variability relative to the other months. Additionally, while all other months have at least 20 observations, March at 7, August at 13 and October at 15 have less data, which should be noted in analysis. The water temperature in the River Severn over the assessment period of the year of 2017 ranges between 2.5 and 24 degrees Celsius and varies following seasonal temperature changes observed in the northern hemisphere such as warmer summers and cooler winters.

2. The second research question is about the relationship between particle size in the river sediments and sample location. It is important to measure particle size to understand the energy

distribution throughout the river system which is related to the velocity or total power of the river. This in turn affects how much sediment the river is able to transport and interact with, thereby shaping the particle size profile of a river. By observing the River Severn at points SEV-A and –B, see figure 1, ahead of the Severn’s interaction with the River Carno, point SEV-C, and after, point SEV-D, it is possible to understand how the two rivers interact. The methods for analysis of this data include the use of the Data Analysis ToolPak add-in on Excel through the descriptive statistics and histogram functions, as well as Z-scores, see appendices 5 and 6, and their respective probabilities. The methods above were chosen to simplify the evaluation process of the data, to determine normal distribution, and to directly compare distributions of different samples.

Clast len. (mm)	SEV-A (Severn Channel)	SEV-D (Severn Point Bar)	SEV-B (Severn Channel)	SEV-C (Carno Channel)
mean	151.02	54.26	130.98	82.29
median	160.20	50.40	112.00	83.20
kurtosis	-0.98	-0.96	-1.18	-1.09
skew	0.03	0.27	0.11	-0.28
std. dev.	67.26	32.96	74.65	34.54

Figure 3: Descriptive statistics table of points SEV-A, -B, -C and -D, n = 50, particle size = discrete ratio data

In figure 3, points SEV-A and –B are located close together before the introduction of the Carno, due to this they are relatively similar with the largest clast lengths of the measured sites.

However, SEV-B appears slightly closer to the bank of the river possibly relating to the smaller lengths of the particles. This is also true for SEV-D as it is located on a point bar after the Carno joins the Severn, though the SEV-C samples also exhibit smaller, though generally larger than SEV-D, particle sizes. Though it doesn’t appear so, all sites are “flat histograms, [which] are platykurtic” demonstrating the multitude of extreme points observed in the data, however the skewness of all sites also establishes a negative skew for all the respective sites’ clast length data (Rogerson, 2015, p.37). Finally, the standard deviation shows the increased variability and spread of particle size in sites SEV-A and –B.

Figure 4a: Histogram of particle size in sites SEV-A. n=50

Figure 4b: Histogram of particle size in sites SEV-D. n=50

Figure 4c: Histogram of particle size in sites SEV-B. n=50

Figure 4d: Histogram of particle size in sites SEV-C. n=50

All the histograms, see figures 4, are simply to visually confirm the irregular distribution within all 4 sites regarding particle size. Despite this lack of normal distribution, z-scores were calculated to standardize and directly compare the distributions of locationally different samples. Additionally, figures 4a and 4c of sites SEV-A and -B have a much larger range of particle sizes than seen in the other sites and their respective figures.

	SEV-A	SEV-D	SEV-B	SEV-C
boulder	256	256	256	256
pebble	64	64	64	64
boulder z	1.56	6.12	1.67	5.03
pebble z	-1.29	0.30	-0.90	-0.53
probability				
boulder+	5.94%	<0.01%	4.75%	<0.01%
pebble-	9.85%	61.41%	18.67%	30.15%

Figure 5: Sizes mm, z-scores, and probability of given boulder and pebble sizes at points SEV-A, -B, -C and -D.

Assuming the size of a boulder is 256mm or greater and a pebble is 64mm or less, figure 5 indicates the probability of either a boulder or pebble existing in all the distinct sites. While pebbles are somewhat likely to exist in SEV-B and -C, they are most common in SEV-D, however, boulders are uncommon in general, with SEV-D and -C containing probably none. These results indicate that though sites SEV-A and -B, and -D and -C are alike, due particularly to proximity in the case of SEV-A and -B, they differ slightly in terms of variation and range of particle sizes throughout the Severn.

3. The third research question considers heavy metal concentrations of zinc (Zn) and lead (Pb) in the two rivers, in addition to nitrogen (N), and how the inclusion of the Carno affects the concentrations in the Severn. Heavy metal concentrations are significant to the quality of rivers and floodplains, as they accumulate in river sediments and pollute arable lands. Nitrogen is common in fertilizers and is known to cause eutrophication and dead zones. Sources of heavy metals such as mines like the Van Mine, and of fertilizer like farming and other agricultural activity, are both common along these two rivers, which is reflected in the data. Observations were collected at points SEV-upstream, -downstream, and CARNO, and are separated seasonally, with data taken in January and July. Analyzed through summary statistics containing sample size, sample average, standard deviation, standard error (68%), and standard error (95%). Additionally, graphically, and through the Data Analysis ToolPak ‘t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances’ for both January and July data separately and comparing the upstream and downstream observations. This was completed to clarify and visualize the data, and to compare the averages between upstream and downstream observations in the Severn.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances			t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances			t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances		
Pb Jan	Sev-U	Sev-Do	Zn Jan	Sev-U	Sev-Do	N Jan	Sev-U	Sev-Do
Mean	42.21647059	57.27419355	Mean	124.0451613	294.24	Mean	1.076666667	1.577142857
Variance	1.294459893	1.981978495	Variance	6.05255914	3.683578947	Variance	0.114264368	0.237109244
Observations	34	31	Observations	31	20	Observations	30	35
Pooled Variance	1.621849703		Pooled Variance	5.133974984		Pooled Variance	0.180561602	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0		Hypothesized Mean Difference	0		Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	63		df	49		df	63	
t Stat	-47.61213176		t Stat	-261.896846		t Stat	-4.733786779	
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.0573E-51		P(T<=t) one-tail	4.65123E-79		P(T<=t) one-tail	6.454E-06	
t Critical one-tail	1.669402222		t Critical one-tail	1.676550893		t Critical one-tail	1.669402222	
P(T<=t) two-tail	4.1146E-51		P(T<=t) two-tail	9.30246E-79		P(T<=t) two-tail	1.2908E-05	
t Critical two-tail	1.998340543		t Critical two-tail	2.009575237		t Critical two-tail	1.998340543	

Figure 6: T-tests function from Data Analysis ToolPak for Pb, Zn, and N between sites SEV-Upstream and – Downstream during January, concentrations = discrete ratio data

The t-stat and t-crit values for these t-tests, see figure 6, show that the SEV-Upstream and – Downstream are significantly different, which means that that alternative hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis stating that there is no difference in heavy metal concentration between the two sites is rejected. Mean concentrations of Pb are visibly different, and Zn values follow this trend with the downstream site containing more than double the concentration of upstream. However, the downstream site has limited observations, at only 20 in comparison to 30 or more from the other sites and data, a notable difference.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances			t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances			t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances		
Pb Jul	Sev-U	Sev-Do	Zn Jul	Sev-U	Sev-Do	N Jul	Sev-U	Sev-Do
Mean	44.47777778	47.61515152	Mean	134.9967742	305.8709677	Mean	1.288235294	1.66969697
Variance	2.233594771	2.091950758	Variance	0.215655914	3.856795699	Variance	0.099857398	0.14655303
Observations	18	33	Observations	31	31	Observations	34	33
Pooled Variance	2.141092558		Pooled Variance	2.036225806		Pooled Variance	0.122846017	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0		Hypothesized Mean Difference	0		Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	49		df	60		df	65	
t Stat	-7.31739788		t Stat	-471.4431809		t Stat	-4.453786553	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.07074E-09		P(T<=t) one-tail	4.4192E-109		P(T<=t) one-tail	1.69811E-05	
t Critical one-tail	1.676550893		t Critical one-tail	1.670648865		t Critical one-tail	1.668635976	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.14147E-09		P(T<=t) two-tail	8.8383E-109		P(T<=t) two-tail	3.39623E-05	
t Critical two-tail	2.009575237		t Critical two-tail	2.000297822		t Critical two-tail	1.997137908	

Figure 7: T-tests function from Data Analysis ToolPak for Pb, Zn, and N between sites SEV-Upstream and – Downstream during July, concentrations = discrete ratio data

Once again, the t-stat and t-crit values for all t-tests in figure 7, establish SEV-Upstream and – Downstream as significantly different, accepting the alternative hypothesis and rejecting the null. Mean concentrations of Pb are less different than January, and similar to January downstream Zn values contain more than double the concentration of upstream. However, in this July data the upstream site for Pb has less observations, at 18 in comparison to more than 30 from the other sites and data. The minimal number of observations is notable but likely not significant as the difference holds true over both seasons for both heavy metals. There are similar statistical differences between N values up and downstream in both January and July, with expectedly higher values in the downstream site and overall increased amounts in summer months when eutrophication proliferates in warmer temperatures. Nitrogen is not, however, related to answering this research question related to heavy metals.

Figure 8: Heavy Metals and Nitrogen in Rivers Severn and Carno Lead (Pb), Zinc (Zn), and Nitrogen (N) concentrations (top to bottom) from January (dark blue) and July (orange) sites SEV-Upstream (yellow vertical rectangle), –Downstream (green vertical rectangle) and CARNO (blue vertical rectangle) including 95% confidence intervals (only large enough to be seen in Nitrogen) additionally note concentration scales do not all begin at 0.

Figure 8 helps to better understand the relationship between the Severn and Carno. The Severn before the Carno intercepts is less contaminated, the Carno which contains significantly increased concentrations of Pb and Zn then mixes with the Severn, which SEV-Downstream reflects. Additionally, though seasonality plays a role, similarly to what the above t-tests demonstrate, the SEV-Upstream has lower concentrations of heavy metals Pb and Zn than – Downstream. This Severn site is comparable to the River West Allen catchment in Northern England, which also exhibited lead and zinc pollution from historical mining operations (Gozzard *et al.*, 2011). Gozzard *et al.* (2011, pp.1-3) describe “point source mine water discharges dominating instream zinc concentration and load”, which would see the Carno with increased concentrations thereby affecting only the downstream Severn observations, as is explicitly seen in the data. However, this study is lacking in assessment period, with only 1 observation year compared to Gozzard’s 17, though both studies lack evaluation of biological factors like indicator species. An additional study by Matthiessen *et al.* (1999) observed sources of heavy metal concentrations in estuarine waters of Essex and Suffolk, however, zinc was found to be attributable to the use of sacrificial nodes by boating traffic. Though boating is not the likely source of heavy metal pollution in the Severn, understanding the various human impacts on water systems is necessary to prescribe efficient conservation techniques. As a result, heavy metals in SEV-Upstream are different and statistically lower than those observed in the - Downstream values.

4. The final research question involves the relation of Severn flow velocity to climatic factors such as air temperature, windspeed, rainfall, and catchment rainfall (total rainfall from the catchment area averaged) to understand how they interact. To predict how future climate change will affect the flow regime is a necessary task to forecast the effects of climate change on this specific locality. To investigate how these factors connect, scatter plots for each climatic factor compared to the flow were created for visual aid, along with a line of best fit to visually represent the data. Pearson’s correlation tests, as well as regression, were also completed through the Data Analysis ToolPak, to establish correlation rather than solely causation, and regression to depict the average relationship between two variables and determine the line of best fit (Rogerson, 2015).

Figure 9a: Severn velocity flow data over a year time frame in 2017

Figure 9b: Scatter plot of Severn flow velocity vs Newton average temperature data. Line of best fit equation and R^2 value in top right corner, $n = 365$

Figure 9c: Scatter plot of Severn flow velocity vs Newton average wind speed data. Line of best fit equation and R^2 value in top right corner, $n = 365$

Figure 9d: Scatter plot of Severn flow velocity vs Newton average rainfall data. Line of best fit equation and R^2 value in top right corner, $n = 365$

Figure 9e: Scatter plot of Severn flow velocity vs upper Severn catchment rainfall data. Line of best fit equation and R^2 value in top right corner, $n = 365$

Figure 9a simply shows the increased flow rate of the Severn in winter months, while the following scatter plots show how flow is related to each respective climatic data, including alpha and r^2 values in the line of best fit. All have visually low correlations, though flow and temperature have a negative relationship, while wind speed, rainfall and catchment rainfall have slightly positive relationships. Particularly flow and catchment rainfall have the highest r^2 value with a 35% relationship strength and flow and temperature the lowest at 9% correlation.

	Date	Flow (cumsecs)	Avg Temp (deg-C)	Avg Wind Speed (m/s)	Avg Rainfall (mm)	Catchment Rainfall (mm)
Date	1.00					
Flow (cumsecs)	0.17	1.00				
Avg Temp (deg-C)	0.49	-0.30	1.00			
Avg Wind Speed (m/s)	0.09	0.49	-0.05	1.00		
Avg Rainfall (mm)	0.12	0.45	-0.02	0.47	1.00	
Catchment Rainfall (mm)	0.12	0.59	-0.10	0.48	0.24	1.00

Figure 10: Correlation function from Data Analysis ToolPak for Severn velocity and Newton climate data, n = 365, flow, wind speed, rainfall and catchment rainfall = discrete ratio, temperature = continuous interval data

The data additionally indicates the moderate strength between flow and catchment rainfall; however, flow is also shown to be moderately correlated to wind speed and average rainfall. Date is undoubtedly related to temperature with a strong to moderate relationship, and as seen above, flow and temperature are weakly negatively correlated. Lastly, wind speed is strongly to moderately positively correlated to rainfall and catchment rainfall, which could be attributed to rainstorms bringing together all these factors. All other climactic factors are weakly related either to each other or to flow velocity. In previously mentioned Gozzard *et al.* (2011), river flow was found to increase concentrations of heavy metals such as zinc found in water samples. Further investigation into this condition regarding the Severn in Caersws could enhance comprehension of research questions 3 and 4, and how they might be connected. Within research question 4, Orr *et al.* (2014) determined a slight increase of river temperatures in England and Wales, however this was largely site specific based on human activity and extreme weather events. Orr *et al.* (2014) established, however, that water flow was found not to affect the water temperature, supporting the weak correlation between the two, seen in above data. It is also inferred that though human activity cannot be directly tied to this and many other polluted water systems, anthropogenic climate change can be tied to the general upward trend of global temperatures. Despite this, Webb (1996) notes that “forecasts must be tentative because future climatic conditions are uncertain and interactions between climate, hydrological and vegetation changes are complex”. This develops the idea of deep rooted climactic and ecosystem interdependence, which causes forming definitive assumptions about relationships between two observations, such as river flow and climactic factors, difficult. Severn flow, date and catchment rainfall and rainfall are somewhat correlated to each other, and Lavers *et al.* (2011) attributes it to Atmospheric Rivers (ARs). ARs are “narrow ribbons along which a large flux of moisture is transported from the subtropics to the mid-latitudes”, though its effects are worsened by warmer temperatures globally, with more moisture stored in the atmosphere and released at once in small localities (Lavers *et al.*, 2011, p.1). The effects of ARs are most clearly seen in winter seasonal flooding

throughout the UK, which is seen in the increased flow rates in the Severn during winter months, see figure 9a. Severn flow and climactic factors are related to each other at various strength levels, though all will be affected by anthropogenic climate change so it is therefore important to protect SSSIs such as these, as Natural England intends to do.

Critical Evaluation

The main concern with the data supporting the first research question is the extremely low number of observations in March, with only 7 data points, though two other months fell far below the average as well. This greatly affects the accuracy of any data analysis, including those descriptive statistics run despite the observation limitations (Rogerson, 2015). The second research question about particle sizes begins with a descriptive statistics table demonstrating the main differences between the sites and additionally shows the lack of normal distribution through the mean and median values. Non-normal distribution is confirmed however by the histograms and disregarded in favor of directly comparing the samples from all 4 sites. Though this is bad statistical practice, it is less unethical if there are many observations (Rogerson, 2015), as is seen in this specific case. Data analysis for the third question were t-tests designed for comparison of locationally and temporally similar observations, such as heavy metal concentrations in January and July respectively. The seasonal aspect of this secondary data allows for additional but unnecessary analysis, in respect to the research question, though it could yield constructive evidence to other existing or further questions. Final research regarding the relation between Severn flow velocity and climactic factors was analyzed with scatter plots, impractical for anything other than visualization of type and strength of relationship (Rogerson, 2015). Additionally, correlation tests to more accurately determine river and climactic relationships, including r values and regression; not pictured as it added little to previously drawn conclusions. Due to the aspect of this secondary data, more information regarding date, time, and locational aspect of observations, including depth, would be a big improvement on clarity. Air humidity specifically would add insight to the full impacts of winter ARs in the UK, as this would also be subject to more variability and extreme events with increased global warming. Additionally, more consistent observation times in the case of March temperature values would decrease the need for uncertainty in related analysis. Moreover, further analysis of these proposed significant relationships, including those containing nitrogen as an affected factor, are essential to confident statistical determination.

Conclusion

Though data collection could be improved, and more information is required to draw absolute conclusions, river flow velocity of the River Severn is related to and affected by various climactic factors. Additionally, there are major differences in heavy metal concentrations between upstream and downstream sites in the Severn, which point to an interference such as the Carno River. Particle size varies throughout the sites with smaller clast lengths seen in the downstream site, and larger clast sizes and ranges seen in upstream sites. Lastly, the water temperature ranges from ~2-25C in the Severn at Caersws, Wales and varies with warmer temperatures in summer months and cooler temperatures in winter. Through critical evaluation of the methods, along with analysis and interpretation of results, methods and context, it has been possible to better understand the current conditions of the Severn in this location. While noting the current and past land-use changes, Natural England wants to observe the site to preserve and improve current conditions in the face of human activity, including the broad impacts of global climate change. Understanding qualities such as water temperature, sediment size, heavy metal concentrations and flow velocity and their spatial, temporal and climactic relationships is a necessary step of comprehending the current and future state of this, and the global environment.

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Appendix

Measured water temperature (°C)												
January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	
6.6	4.3	4	12.8	17	20	14	18.3	12	6.9	12.3	4.3	
4.4	5.6	3.4	9.1	12.5	15.8	14.1	16.7	10.6	7.6	6.3	5.4	
5.3	5.9	11.3	11.8	14	16	18.1	19.2	14	9.5	2.7	4	
6.5	5.8	7.2	13.6	15.3	16.6	19	19.2	12.4	11.4	11.8	5.8	
5.3	4	11.2	9.7	12.5	17.6	20	20.1	10.7	12.6	3.9	4.9	
6.9	4.3	6.2	12.6	17.4	15.3	18.5	19.8	8.4	11.1	10.2	5.6	
4.9	4.9	3.1	14.1	16	19	14.3	18.4	10.6	5.4	7.2	5.4	
5	4.5		12.5	13.3	17.4	15.3	19.5	10.9	9.3	8.5	4.7	
5	5.9		9.7	11.3	26.7	15.4	18.6	13.9	3.7	5	5.2	
5.8	5.1		11.7	15.6	16.8	16.1	20.8	10.5	8.6	7.2	5.1	
3.4	5.8		12.7	18.5	19	22.1	18.4	14.9	2	4.6	5.9	
4.5	5.8		8	15.9	13	15.4	18.7	11.5	10	7.1	5.6	
3.4	5.4		13.2	14.2	20.8	14.5	16.7	9	6.1	9.8	4.5	
4.9	5.1		14.8	17.6	20.4	21.5		12.1	8.6	6.8	4.8	
4.5	4.3		8.3	18.3	14.1	16.7		10.1	6.4	10.1	5.9	
5.8	6.3		15.9	17.2	21.8	24.1		17.9		9.1	8.1	
3.9	4.6		15.7	19.2	16.9	18.7		14.6		4.7	6.8	
5.2	4.1		11.7	14.4	16.1	20.4		12.3		6.7	6.9	
6.8	5.1		5.5	12.5	12.9	14.5		13.4		8.7	5.9	
6.8	5.1		5.5	12.5	12.9	14.5		13.4		8.7	5.9	
6.2	5.9		6.5	11.3		15.6		14.5		7.9		
	4.8		12.5	13.1		17.6		14.5		6.9		
	5.1		5.5	12.5		14.5		13.4		8.7		

Appendix 1: Raw temperature data at site SEV-1

Measured water temperature (2017) (°C)												
	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
number observ.s	21.00	23.00	7.00	23.00	23.00	20.00	23.00	13.00	23.00	15.00	23.00	20.00
min	3.40	4.00	3.10	5.50	11.30	12.90	14.00	16.70	8.40	2.00	2.70	4.00
max	6.90	6.30	11.30	15.90	19.20	26.70	24.10	20.80	17.90	12.60	12.30	8.10
range	3.50	2.30	8.20	10.40	7.90	13.80	10.10	4.10	9.50	10.60	9.60	4.10
median	5.20	5.10	6.20	11.80	14.40	16.85	16.10	18.70	12.30	8.60	7.20	5.50
median 1 Quartile	4.50	4.55	3.70	8.70	12.50	15.68	14.50	18.40	10.65	6.25	6.50	4.88
median 3 Quartile	6.20	5.80	9.20	13.00	17.10	19.25	18.85	19.50	13.95	9.75	8.90	5.90
interQuart. Range	1.70	1.25	5.50	4.30	4.60	3.58	4.35	1.10	3.30	3.50	2.40	1.03
mean	5.29	5.12	6.63	11.02	14.87	17.46	17.17	18.80	12.42	7.95	7.60	5.54
standard deviation	1.08	0.68	3.49	3.24	2.44	3.41	2.92	1.19	2.21	2.92	2.43	0.96

Appendix 2: Descriptive statistics table at site SEV-1

Clast numbe	Clast length (mm)			
	SEV-A (Severn)	SEV-D (Severn)	SEV-B (Severn Channel)	SEV-C (Carno Channel)
1	31.2	12.9	85.3	81.7
2	33.9	29.5	164.1	48.9
3	49.8	72	12.6	82.7
4	56.9	96.9	238.7	32.1
5	60.9	19	10.2	112.8
6	61.6	77.1	88	84.8
7	63.3	105.7	119.2	123.1
8	64.8	84.5	234.1	72.1
9	71.3	31.9	14	94.9
10	76.2	33.2	98.2	127.3
11	94.4	88.3	228.1	22.6
12	100.1	8.1	199.1	59.4
13	100.5	52.1	75.4	45.7
14	102.3	48.7	78.5	39.4
15	104.5	70	89.2	83.7
16	107.7	18.9	261.9	34.6
17	112.2	53	178.7	10.4
18	113.3	23.9	50.8	130.7
19	122.9	9.5	145.8	129.4
20	125.6	88.7	111.6	97.9
21	127.4	12.1	34.8	78
22	130.2	117.9	80.9	131.3
23	145.6	5.7	223.3	112.2
24	159.9	29.3	191.5	72.2
25	160	70	165.9	77.2
26	160.4	87.1	226.3	122.9
27	161.1	61.6	157.4	101.8
28	161.5	39.9	146.1	126.9
29	162.6	85.5	44.4	63.5
30	166.3	62.8	217.8	116
31	176	60.8	78.4	128.2
32	176	12.2	229.3	55.6
33	176.8	60.4	88.5	61.7
34	179.5	40.5	124.6	49.3
35	193.3	3.21	75	112.1
36	194.4	46.4	183.7	66.2
37	196.5	37.4	96.9	79.8
38	197.3	84	100.8	114.8
39	200	87.9	240.9	116.2
40	209	29.8	112.4	92.6
41	221.9	46.8	14.9	108.2
42	226.9	31.7	98	118.3
43	230.1	89.8	247.1	49
44	233.7	81.7	200.9	33.5
45	237.1	83.6	10.4	105.4
46	254.3	14.7	71.8	22.3
47	256.3	30.2	231	98.7
48	267.3	36.6	76.4	102.3
49	268.3	123.1	196.7	50.5
50	267.8	116.5	99.2	33.4

Appendix 3: Raw sediment particle data sites SEV-A, -B, -C and -D

SEV- A		SEV - C	
Mean	151.018	Mean	82.286
Standard Error	9.511881	Standard Error	4.884519
Median	160.2	Median	83.2
Mode	176	Mode	#N/A
Standard Deviation	67.25916	Standard Deviation	34.53877
Sample Variance	4523.794	Sample Variance	1192.927
Kurtosis	-0.9774	Kurtosis	-1.09301
Skewness	0.033745	Skewness	-0.28185
Range	237.1	Range	120.9
Minimum	31.2	Minimum	10.4
Maximum	268.3	Maximum	131.3
Sum	7550.9	Sum	4114.3
Count	50	Count	50
Confidence Level(95.0%)	19.11484	Confidence Level(95.0%)	9.815809
SEV - B		SEV - D	
Mean	130.976	Mean	54.2622
Standard Error	10.55711	Standard Error	4.660766
Median	112	Median	50.4
Mode	#N/A	Mode	70
Standard Deviation	74.65004	Standard Deviation	32.95659
Sample Variance	5572.629	Sample Variance	1086.137
Kurtosis	-1.17832	Kurtosis	-0.9578
Skewness	0.109816	Skewness	0.268654
Range	251.7	Range	119.89
Minimum	10.2	Minimum	3.21
Maximum	261.9	Maximum	123.1
Sum	6548.8	Sum	2713.11
Count	50	Count	50
Confidence Level(95.0%)	21.21531	Confidence Level(95.0%)	9.36616

Appendix 4: Descriptive statistics function from Data Analysis ToolPak for sites SEV –A, -B, -C, and –D

z	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.09
-3.6	.0002	.0002	.0001	.0001	.0001	.0001	.0001	.0001	.0001	.0001
-3.5	.0002	.0002	.0002	.0002	.0002	.0002	.0002	.0002	.0002	.0002
-3.4	.0003	.0003	.0003	.0003	.0003	.0003	.0003	.0003	.0003	.0002
-3.3	.0005	.0005	.0005	.0004	.0004	.0004	.0004	.0004	.0004	.0003
-3.2	.0007	.0007	.0006	.0006	.0006	.0006	.0006	.0005	.0005	.0005
-3.1	.0010	.0009	.0009	.0009	.0008	.0008	.0008	.0008	.0007	.0007
-3.0	.0013	.0013	.0013	.0012	.0012	.0011	.0011	.0011	.0010	.0010
-2.9	.0019	.0018	.0018	.0017	.0016	.0016	.0015	.0015	.0014	.0014
-2.8	.0026	.0025	.0024	.0023	.0023	.0022	.0021	.0021	.0020	.0019
-2.7	.0035	.0034	.0033	.0032	.0031	.0030	.0029	.0028	.0027	.0026
-2.6	.0047	.0045	.0044	.0043	.0041	.0040	.0039	.0038	.0037	.0036
-2.5	.0062	.0060	.0059	.0057	.0055	.0054	.0052	.0051	.0049	.0048
-2.4	.0082	.0080	.0078	.0075	.0073	.0071	.0069	.0068	.0066	.0064
-2.3	.0107	.0104	.0102	.0099	.0096	.0094	.0091	.0089	.0087	.0084
-2.2	.0139	.0136	.0132	.0129	.0125	.0122	.0119	.0116	.0113	.0110
-2.1	.0179	.0174	.0170	.0166	.0162	.0158	.0154	.0150	.0146	.0143
-2.0	.0228	.0222	.0217	.0212	.0207	.0202	.0197	.0192	.0188	.0183
-1.9	.0287	.0281	.0274	.0268	.0262	.0256	.0250	.0244	.0239	.0233
-1.8	.0359	.0351	.0344	.0336	.0329	.0322	.0314	.0307	.0301	.0294
-1.7	.0446	.0436	.0427	.0418	.0409	.0401	.0392	.0384	.0375	.0367
-1.6	.0548	.0537	.0526	.0516	.0505	.0495	.0485	.0475	.0465	.0455
-1.5	.0668	.0655	.0643	.0630	.0618	.0606	.0594	.0582	.0571	.0559
-1.4	.0808	.0793	.0778	.0764	.0749	.0735	.0721	.0708	.0694	.0681
-1.3	.0968	.0951	.0934	.0918	.0901	.0885	.0869	.0853	.0838	.0823
-1.2	.1151	.1131	.1112	.1093	.1075	.1056	.1038	.1020	.1003	.0985
-1.1	.1357	.1335	.1314	.1292	.1271	.1251	.1230	.1210	.1190	.1170
-1.0	.1587	.1562	.1539	.1515	.1492	.1469	.1446	.1423	.1401	.1379
-0.9	.1841	.1814	.1788	.1762	.1736	.1711	.1685	.1660	.1635	.1611
-0.8	.2119	.2090	.2061	.2033	.2005	.1977	.1949	.1922	.1894	.1867
-0.7	.2420	.2389	.2358	.2327	.2296	.2266	.2236	.2206	.2177	.2148
-0.6	.2743	.2709	.2676	.2643	.2611	.2578	.2546	.2514	.2483	.2451
-0.5	.3085	.3050	.3015	.2981	.2946	.2912	.2877	.2843	.2810	.2776
-0.4	.3446	.3409	.3372	.3336	.3300	.3264	.3228	.3192	.3156	.3121
-0.3	.3821	.3783	.3745	.3707	.3669	.3632	.3594	.3557	.3520	.3483
-0.2	.4207	.4168	.4129	.4090	.4052	.4013	.3974	.3936	.3897	.3859
-0.1	.4602	.4562	.4522	.4483	.4443	.4404	.4364	.4325	.4286	.4247
-0.0	.5000	.4960	.4920	.4880	.4840	.4801	.4761	.4721	.4681	.4641

Appendix 5: Z-score chart for (-) particle sizes (mm), sites SEV -A, -B, -C, and -D

Number in the
table represents
 $P(Z \leq z)$

z	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.09
0.0	.5000	.5040	.5080	.5120	.5160	.5199	.5239	.5279	.5319	.5359
0.1	.5398	.5438	.5478	.5517	.5557	.5596	.5636	.5675	.5714	.5753
0.2	.5793	.5832	.5871	.5910	.5948	.5987	.6026	.6064	.6103	.6141
0.3	.6179	.6217	.6255	.6293	.6331	.6368	.6406	.6443	.6480	.6517
0.4	.6554	.6591	.6628	.6664	.6700	.6736	.6772	.6808	.6844	.6879
0.5	.6915	.6950	.6985	.7019	.7054	.7088	.7123	.7157	.7190	.7224
0.6	.7257	.7291	.7324	.7357	.7389	.7422	.7454	.7486	.7517	.7549
0.7	.7580	.7611	.7642	.7673	.7704	.7734	.7764	.7794	.7823	.7852
0.8	.7881	.7910	.7939	.7967	.7995	.8023	.8051	.8078	.8106	.8133
0.9	.8159	.8186	.8212	.8238	.8264	.8289	.8315	.8340	.8365	.8389
1.0	.8413	.8438	.8461	.8485	.8508	.8531	.8554	.8577	.8599	.8621
1.1	.8643	.8665	.8686	.8708	.8729	.8749	.8770	.8790	.8810	.8830
1.2	.8849	.8869	.8888	.8907	.8925	.8944	.8962	.8980	.8997	.9015
1.3	.9032	.9049	.9066	.9082	.9099	.9115	.9131	.9147	.9162	.9177
1.4	.9192	.9207	.9222	.9236	.9251	.9265	.9279	.9292	.9306	.9319
1.5	.9332	.9345	.9357	.9370	.9382	.9394	.9406	.9418	.9429	.9441
1.6	.9452	.9463	.9474	.9484	.9495	.9505	.9515	.9525	.9535	.9545
1.7	.9554	.9564	.9573	.9582	.9591	.9599	.9608	.9616	.9625	.9633
1.8	.9641	.9649	.9656	.9664	.9671	.9678	.9686	.9693	.9699	.9706
1.9	.9713	.9719	.9726	.9732	.9738	.9744	.9750	.9756	.9761	.9767
2.0	.9772	.9778	.9783	.9788	.9793	.9798	.9803	.9808	.9812	.9817
2.1	.9821	.9826	.9830	.9834	.9838	.9842	.9846	.9850	.9854	.9857
2.2	.9861	.9864	.9868	.9871	.9875	.9878	.9881	.9884	.9887	.9890
2.3	.9893	.9896	.9898	.9901	.9904	.9906	.9909	.9911	.9913	.9916
2.4	.9918	.9920	.9922	.9925	.9927	.9929	.9931	.9932	.9934	.9936
2.5	.9938	.9940	.9941	.9943	.9945	.9946	.9948	.9949	.9951	.9952
2.6	.9953	.9955	.9956	.9957	.9959	.9960	.9961	.9962	.9963	.9964
2.7	.9965	.9966	.9967	.9968	.9969	.9970	.9971	.9972	.9973	.9974
2.8	.9974	.9975	.9976	.9977	.9977	.9978	.9979	.9979	.9980	.9981
2.9	.9981	.9982	.9982	.9983	.9984	.9984	.9985	.9985	.9986	.9986
3.0	.9987	.9987	.9987	.9988	.9988	.9989	.9989	.9989	.9990	.9990
3.1	.9990	.9991	.9991	.9991	.9992	.9992	.9992	.9992	.9993	.9993
3.2	.9993	.9993	.9994	.9994	.9994	.9994	.9994	.9995	.9995	.9995
3.3	.9995	.9995	.9995	.9996	.9996	.9996	.9996	.9996	.9996	.9997
3.4	.9997	.9997	.9997	.9997	.9997	.9997	.9997	.9997	.9997	.9998
3.5	.9998	.9998	.9998	.9998	.9998	.9998	.9998	.9998	.9998	.9998
3.6	.9998	.9998	.9999	.9999	.9999	.9999	.9999	.9999	.9999	.9999

Appendix 6: Z-score chart for (+) particle sizes (mm), sites SEV -A, -B, -C, and -D

z score	SEV-A (Severn)	SEV-D (Severn)	SEV-B (Severn Channel)	SEV-C (Carno Channel)
	-1.7814377	-1.255050818	-0.611868375	-0.016966442
	-1.7412945	-0.751357988	0.443723795	-0.966623924
	-1.5048955	0.538217029	-1.585745922	0.01198653
	-1.3993336	1.293756274	1.443053437	-1.453033854
	-1.3398622	-1.069958874	-1.617895937	0.883470988
	-1.3294547	0.692966031	-0.575699608	0.072787772
	-1.3041793	1.56077416	-0.157749408	1.1816866
	-1.2818775	0.917503799	1.381432575	-0.294914973
	-1.1852364	-0.678534928	-1.566991747	0.365212789
	-1.1123839	-0.639089104	-0.439062043	1.303289082
	-0.8417887	1.032806977	1.301057536	-1.728087088
	-0.7570419	-1.400696937	0.912578185	-0.662617718
	-0.7510948	-0.065607508	-0.744487188	-1.059273434
	-0.7243326	-0.16877351	-0.702960085	-1.241677158
	-0.6916233	0.477531146	-0.5596246	0.040939502
	-0.6440461	-1.072993168	1.753836919	-1.380651424
	-0.5771407	-0.038298861	0.639303055	-2.081313346
	-0.5607861	-0.921278461	-1.074024845	1.401729187
	-0.4180546	-1.358216819	0.198579928	1.364090324
	-0.3779114	1.044944153	-0.25955779	0.452071705
	-0.3511492	-1.279325171	-1.28835828	-0.124092438
	-0.3095192	1.930958047	-0.67081007	1.41910097
	-0.0805541	-1.473519997	1.236757506	0.866099205
	0.13205637	-0.757426576	0.810769803	-0.292019676
	0.13354316	0.477531146	0.467836306	-0.147254816
	0.1394903	0.996395447	1.276945025	1.175896005
	0.14989781	0.222650437	0.353971669	0.564988296
	0.15584495	-0.435791395	0.20259868	1.291707893
	0.1721996	0.94784674	-1.159758219	-0.543910532
	0.2272107	0.259061967	1.163080387	0.976120499
	0.37142898	0.198376083	-0.704299669	1.329346757
	0.37142898	-1.276290877	1.317132544	-0.772639011
	0.38332327	0.186238907	-0.569001688	-0.596025882
	0.4234665	-0.417585631	-0.085411874	-0.955042735
	0.62864303	-1.549073922	-0.749845524	0.863203908
	0.64499768	-0.238562275	0.706282253	-0.465737508
	0.67622019	-0.511648749	-0.456476634	-0.071977088
	0.68811449	0.902332328	-0.404232859	0.941376932
	0.72825772	1.0206698	1.472524285	0.981911093
	0.8620685	-0.742255105	-0.248841119	0.298620953
	1.05386394	-0.226425099	-1.554935491	0.750287317
	1.12820326	-0.684603516	-0.44174121	1.042712334
	1.17578043	1.078321389	1.555578491	-0.963728626
	1.22930474	0.832543562	0.936690696	-1.412499693
	1.27985548	0.890195151	-1.615216769	0.669218995
	1.53558274	-1.200433523	-0.792712211	-1.736772979
	1.56531847	-0.730117929	1.339905472	0.475234083
	1.72886497	-0.535923103	-0.731091348	0.579464782
	1.74373284	2.088741343	0.880428169	-0.920299168
	1.7362989	1.888477929	-0.425666203	-1.41539499
	-2.2453151	-1.646474764	-1.754533503	-2.382424255

Appendix 7: Z-scores of raw sediment particle data sites SEV-A, -B, -C and -D

Severn Upstream					
Sev-U Pb Jan mg/l	Sev-Pb Jul mg/l	Sev-U Zn Jan mg/l	Sev-U Zn Jul mg/l	Sev-U N Jan mg/l	Sev-U N Jul mg/l
42.1	44.1	121.2	135	1	1.5
43.5	45.9	125.8	134.9	0.7	1.7
43.7	43.7	127.4	135.9	0.9	1
41	45.1	126.5	135.5	0.6	0.8
40.4	43.5	120.3	135.6	1.3	0.9
41.4	42.3	120.3	135.3	0.6	1.6
41.8	42.8	122.4	134.5	0.8	1.4
42	46.4	120.6	134.3	0.8	0.9
43	42.9	123.4	135.3	0.6	1.7
43.4	43.5	123.6	134.2	1.2	1.9
40.9	46.7	127	135.4	1.4	1.2
41.4	43.7	123.1	135.5	1.5	1.1
41.78	44.3	120.9	135.1	0.7	1.8
42.1	43	126.3	134.4	1.5	1.2
42.1	46.6	121.8	135.3	1.3	1.2
42.7	46.8	126.8	134.6	0.6	1.4
42.5	43.8	122.8	135.2	1.2	1
40.6	45.5	127	135.2	1.6	1.2
41.56		126	134.7	1.2	1.8
41.4		124.3	134.8	1	1.3
40.5		122.8	135.1	1.1	1.2
44.5		124.7	134.5	1.4	1.1
43		127.7	135.8	0.8	0.9
42		122.5	134.7	0.6	1.1
44.1		125	134.9	1.5	1.4
42.9		121.4	135	1.7	1.7
43.1		127.9	134.7	1.3	0.8
42.3		126.8	135.7	1.1	1.3
42.2		124.6	134.6	1.2	1.1
40.72		123.6	134.3	1.1	1.1
41.4		120.9	134.9		1.2
41.2					1.8
44.4					1
43.7					1.5
					0.8

Appendix 8: Raw Pb, Zn, N data site SEV-Upstream

Severn Downstream					
Sev-Do Pb Jan mg/l	Sev-Do Pb Jul mg/l	Sev-Do Zn Jan mg/l	Sev-Do Zn Jul mg/l	Sev-Do N Jan mg/l	Sev-Do N Jul mg/l
57.1	49.6	290.1	309.4	1.8	2.2
57.3	49.7	295.9	306	1.6	1.8
57.1	47	291.2	302.8	0.9	1.6
57.6	45.9	295.6	307	2	1.7
56.5	47.9	292.6	309.3	1.8	2.1
56.7	46.7	293.8	305.6	1.5	1.1
59.3	49.1	293.8	305.6	1.2	2.1
58.9	49.1	295.1	306.9	1.8	1.5
55.2	47.5	293.3	303.9	1.4	1.3
55.1	48.6	295.7	303.8	2.1	1.7
55.5	47.9	292.7	305	0.9	1.2
56.9	49.9	296.9	304	1.1	1.5
58.4	48.5	297.3	308.8	2.3	1.6
58.4	46.4	294	308.1	0.9	2.1
59	47.6	294.1	306.1	2.2	2
58.9	47.1	293	309	2.2	1.5
55.9	48.5	295.6	305.1	0.8	1.6
55.4	45.4	292.6	304.2	1.5	1.3
57.2	45.2	294.6	305.9	1.4	1.2
57.9	46.1	296.9	306.3	1.7	1.6
56.3	46.4		308.8	1.6	0.9
56.4	47.5		304.6	1.1	1.5
59.9	45.7		307.3	1.4	2.3
58.5	45.2		305.5	1.2	1.9
58.1	45.9		305.9	2	1.9
56.6	49.9		303.3	2.4	1.4
56	47.2		305.2	1.8	2.3
59.2	48.8		307.4	2.4	1.5
55.9	49.3		305.5	1.4	2.4
55.3	47.3		302.9	0.9	1.5
59	48		302.8	1.8	1.8
	47			0.8	1.9
	49.4			1.2	1.1
				2.1	
				2	

Appendix 9: Raw Pb, Zn, N data site SEV-Downstream

Carno					
Car Pb Jan	Car Pb Jul	Car Zn Jan	Car Zn Jul	Car N Jan	Car N Jul
mg/l	mg/l	mg/l	mg/l	mg/l	mg/l
84.2	88.7	405.6	444.7	1.8	1.8
81.6	88.6	403.9	446.4	1.9	1.3
81.1	86.7	406.7	449.3	1	1.8
81.7	86.6	401.7	442.2	1	1.8
81.4	85.5	403.2	443.3	0.8	1.9
82.4	85.6	400.3	445	1.6	2.1
82.5	86	401.6	448.7	1.6	2
84.5	86.1	400.6	447.9	1.8	1.6
83.2	86.1	400.9	448.3	1.2	1.4
83.6	86.5	404.8	449.9	0.8	2.1
84.2	86.5	406.7	449.9	1.9	1.1
81.7	86.6	406.6	448	1.1	1
83.1	87.1	403.1	443	1	1
82.3	87.1	403.3	446.4	1.3	1.7
82.6	87.2	404.3	444.2	1.1	1
80.9	87.6	402.6	448.1		1.1
83.7	87.7	403.6	444.5		1.5
82.7	87.8	405.2	449.7		2.1
82.9	87.8	406.1	445.4		1.5
84.2	87.9	407	445		1.5
83.3	88	405.7	446.4		2
82.2	88.1	401.8	444		1.7
82.7	88.2	404.9	449.5		1.3
82.1	88.4	404	447.3		1.4
83.9	88.4	405.9	445.1		1.6
81.3	88.5	401.1	443.6		1.3
84.2	88.6	402.4	449.4		1.7
82.1	89.3	406.6	447.7		1.1
83.4	89.3	407.8	446.1		1.7
83	89.4	405.4	445.6		1.3
84.6	89.4	402.9	442.2		2
81.4	89.6				1.6
81.7	89.7				1.8
83	86.2				1.3
80.5	87.1				1.6
81.1	89.9				
81.2					
81.7					

Appendix 10: Raw Pb, Zn, N data site CARNO

Appendix 11: Descriptive statistics data table site SEV-Upstream and original Pb concentrations by site graphic

Appendix 12: Descriptive statistics data table site SEV-Downstream and original Zn concentrations by site graphic

	Carno					
	Car Pb Jan	Car Pb Jul	Car Zn Jan	Car Zn Jul	Car N Jan	Car N Jul
	mg/l	mg/l	mg/l	mg/l	mg/l	mg/l
sample number	38	36	31	31	15	35
sample mean	82.6	87.7	404.1	446.3	1.3	1.6
std. dev.	1.1	1.3	2.1	2.4	0.4	0.3
std. error (68%)	0.18	0.21	0.38	0.43	0.10	0.06
std. error (95%)	0.36	0.41	0.75	0.84	0.20	0.11

Appendix 13: Descriptive statistics data table site CARNO and original N concentrations by site graphic

SUMMARY OUTPUT															
Regression Statistics					y = bx + a										
Multiple R	0.590821532	r-value	y = catchment rainfall coefficient * x + intercept coefficient												
R Square	0.349070083	determines goodness of fit	y = 2.32 * x + 8.12												
Adjusted R Square	0.347276888		river flow based on daily catchment rainfall of 20mm												
Standard Error	18.76953958		y = 2.32 * 20 + 8.12												
Observations	365		y = 54.52												
ANOVA															
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F										
Regression	1	68579.17568	68579.17568	194.6637	1.01042E-35	avg distance from line of best fit									
Residual	363	127883.3086	352.2956161												
Total	364	196462.4843													
Coefficients															
Intercept	8.116426919	Standard Error	1.186918024	t Stat	6.838237144	P-value	3.41E-11	Lower 95%	5.782328126	Upper 95%	10.45052571	Lower 95.0%	5.782328126	Upper 95.0%	10.45052571
Catchment rainfall- Upper Severn (mm)	2.321356632	Standard Error	0.166379324	t Stat	13.95219415	P-value	1.01E-35	Lower 95%	1.994168257	Upper 95%	2.648545007	Lower 95.0%	1.994168257	Upper 95.0%	2.648545007

Appendix 14: Regression function from Data Analysis ToolPak for Severn flow and catchment rainfall (upper Severn mm)

SUMMARY OUTPUT								
<i>Regression Statistics</i>								
Multiple R	0.453883443	y = bx + a						
R Square	0.206010179	y = avg rainfall coefficient * x + intercept coefficient						
Adjusted R Square	0.20382288	y = 1.26 * x + 10.3						
Standard Error	20.72974551	river flow based on daily avg rainfall of 20mm						
Observations	365	y = 1.26 * 20 + 10.3						
ANOVA								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	1	40473.27164	40473.27164	94.18470261	5.97974E-20			
Residual	363	155989.2127	429.722349					
Total	364	196462.4843						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	10.31779984	1.308127603	7.887456707	3.66036E-14	7.745339906	12.89025977	7.745339906	12.89025977
Average Rainfall - Newtown (mm)	1.262121743	0.130050212	9.70488035	5.97974E-20	1.006375318	1.517868169	1.006375318	1.517868169

Appendix 15: Regression function from Data Analysis ToolPak for Severn flow and average rainfall (Newton mm)

SUMMARY OUTPUT								
<i>Regression Statistics</i>								
Multiple R	0.492544586	y = bx + a						
R Square	0.242600169	y = wind speed coefficient * x + intercept coefficient						
Adjusted R Square	0.240513668	y = 1.94 * x + -2.2						
Standard Error	20.24646025	river flow based on daily wind speed of 20m/s						
Observations	365	y = 1.94 * 20 + -2.2						
ANOVA								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	1	47661.83184	47661.83184	116.2712977	1.05E-23			
Residual	363	148800.6525	409.9191528					
Total	364	196462.4843						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	-2.160370276	2.101593152	-1.027967889	0.304649411	-6.293196587	1.972456034	-6.293196587	1.972456034
Average Wind Speed- Newtown (m/s)	1.943618279	0.180249768	10.78291694	1.0547E-23	1.589153389	2.298083169	1.589153389	2.298083169

Appendix 16: Regression function from Data Analysis ToolPak for Severn flow and average wind speed (Newton m/s)

SUMMARY OUTPUT								
<i>Regression Statistics</i>								
Multiple R	0.300353736	y = bx + a						
R Square	0.090212367	y = avg temp coefficient * x + intercept coefficient						
Adjusted R Square	0.087706065	y = -1.8 * x + 32						
Standard Error	22.18995992	river flow based on daily avg temp of 20C						
Observations	365	y = -1.8 * 20 + 32						
ANOVA								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	1	17723.34571	17723.34571	35.99421224	4.79071E-09			
Residual	363	178739.1386	492.3943212					
Total	364	196462.4843						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	31.9890301	2.693514709	11.87631536	1.04667E-27	26.69217783	37.28588237	26.69217783	37.28588237
Average Temperature - Newtown (deg-C)	-1.762816253	0.293826329	-5.999517667	4.79071E-09	-2.340631795	-1.185000712	-2.340631795	-1.185000712

Appendix 17: Regression function from Data Analysis ToolPak for Severn flow and average temperature (Newton C)